

COMPETENCIES OF JOURNALISM STUDENTS: SKILLS AND THE IMPORTANCE OF KNOWLEDGE

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Abstract. *The article is based on the professional competence of a future journalist, the axiological component of professional competence and the praxeological component of the professional competence of journalism students based on 8 groups of skills. Changes in the role and significance of information in the activity and development of society, as well as the object and subject of information professional activity, the relevance of studying the problems of training journalists in educational institutions, and contradictions are highlighted.*

Keywords: *gnostic, analytical, communicative, constructive, competence-based, reproductive, component, praxeological, globalization.*

The professional qualification of a journalist cannot be realized without the axiological component of professional competence. Not only skills and knowledge are important, but also the attitude towards the profession, especially the mass media, and the whole society. The axiological aspect is particularly evident in the profession of journalism, it manifests itself in every program, report, material, and shows the journalist's valuable attitude to events and people. The development of the axiological component noted in the experimental work is characterized as pragmatic, emotional, value. The praxeological component of professional competence of student journalists is based on 8 groups of skills: gnostic, analytical, design, communicative, constructive, creative, evaluation, information. Pedagogical conditions that ensure formation of professional competence of journalism students in interaction between Dekmak, educational institution and mass media are as follows:

- real participation of journalist-students in mass media activities (radio broadcasting and television programs or creation of materials for the press);
- creative and valuable position of the student in the development of professional knowledge and skills;
- cases of purposeful formation of professional skills of student journalists (ie praxeological component of competence);
- axiological potential of mutual cooperation between the educational institution and mass media;
- full-fledged scientific and pedagogical activity of leading experts in the mass media in the educational process of training student journalists in educational institutions;
- creation of an educational creative-production laboratory based on the use of a competency-based approach and renewal of the principles of subjectivity, variability, and creativity; for the formation of competence, it is necessary to develop professionally oriented tasks of a creative nature.

“The concept of competence is broader than the concepts of knowledge, skills or competence, competence includes them as a result of education (but competence is not a simple sum of knowledge, skills and competences, but a concept with a slightly different content)”.

The concept of competence includes not only cognitive and operational-technological, but also motivational, moral and social components.

Currently, the education system is undergoing profound changes that are closely related to changes in the economic and socio-political spheres of society. Modernization of higher professional education ensures that the quality of training of specialists meets the requirements of modern world realities. The competence of educational efficiency was also supported by scientist S.I.Zair-Bek. He considers the development of intellectual and creative potential of students in the acquisition of certain knowledge to be the most important task in education, which allows further production of new knowledge and development of knowledge. The training of professional journalists in higher educational institutions has its own characteristics and reflects the sharp contradictions of the past, the increasing role of mass media in the life of modern society. At this point, he emphasized that “education based on a competent approach is education aimed at the formation of competences to apply knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by students in practice in personal, professional and social activities”.

The change in the role and importance of information in the activity and development of society inevitably creates new requirements in terms of quality for those who professionally deal with information, that is, the object and subject of information professional activity, and those who are its result. Realization of the journalist's social and professional responsibility in the information society directly depends on the high civil maturity and professional skills of the subject of activity. Therefore, it is necessary to develop the skills of student journalists. The urgency of studying the problems of training journalists in educational institutions is connected with contradictions:

- between society's high demand for professionally qualified and responsible journalists and the level of real culture of specialists working in mass media;
- between the rapidly changing situation in the development of communication and the lack of professional competence of graduates, their readiness to work with modern technical equipment;
- the increase in requirements for the journalist's mobility and the traditional methods of organizing the educational process in educational institutions.

Analyzing the state of the problem of training journalist personnel, emphasizing the high scientific development of the issue and the uncertainty of looking at the content and methodology of professional training of student journalists, the fund of knowledge in science has been formed and collected, which allows studying the identified research problem.

The analysis of philosophical, psychological, pedagogical literature shows the possibility of creating effective conditions for the formation of professional competence of student journalists. At the same time, it should be admitted that the staging of journalism education has not been studied from this point of view. A special experiment was not created for the implementation of one of the models that can be formed in the “Educational institutions - mass media” system. This determined the selection of a special research topic "Interaction between educational institutions and mass media as a factor in the formation of professional competence of student journalists”.

The purpose of the research: theoretically and practically justifying the pedagogical conditions for the formation of the professional competence of journalist-students.

Research object: mutual cooperation of educational institutions and mass media in training journalists.

Research subject: formation of professional competence of student journalists.

Research hypothesis: interaction between educational institutions and mass media is an effective factor in the formation of professional competence of journalism students, if:

- Real participation of student journalists in mass media activities is ensured (creating materials for radio broadcasting and television programs);
- the student's creative value position is implemented in the development of professional knowledge and skills;
- situations are created for the purposeful formation of the professional skills of student journalists (that is, the praxeological component of competence);
- the axiological potential of mutual cooperation between educational institutions and mass media will be updated;
- Full-fledged scientific and pedagogical activity is guaranteed during the educational process of training student journalists with media leading experts.

Based on the goal, topic, research hypothesis, the following research tasks were defined:

- systematization of theoretical knowledge on the problem of the interaction of pedagogy and specialized practice in the educational process in the training of journalists in an educational institution;
- to determine the most effective forms of interaction between educational institutions and the mass media, as well as the pedagogical conditions for the formation of the professional competence of specialists with higher journalistic education;
- development of guidelines for the introduction of the journalist personnel training system in cooperation with educational institutions and mass media

Development of information security competence in future journalists as a social necessity

The theoretical and methodological basis of the research is the basic rules of the theory of activity, the theory of values, as well as the competence-based approach to the system of theoretical rules necessary for setting, studying and solving the problem of society formation. In relation to professional ethics, social responsibility, observance and protection of the rights and interests of society and citizens. Research methods include understanding and theoretical analysis of scientific literature, analytical observation, questioning and interview, pedagogical experiment, analysis of information products and educational tasks performed by intern students, analysis of professional activities of graduates.

Scientific novelty and theoretical significance of the research:

- the concept of professional competence of journalists as an integral unit of knowledge, skills, relations was clarified; the classification of the main professional skills is revealed and based: gnostic (cognitive), analytical, design, communicative, constructive, creative, evaluation, information;
- a set of pedagogical conditions for the formation of the professional competence of journalist-students is defined:

Defense rules:

The essence of the interaction between practice and theory in the educational process is to reveal the creative resources of the individual in the process of performing the educational and production tasks specially assigned to the student within the framework of the individual curriculum developed on the basis of the educational process. is to give.

In order to build a model of development of socially active civic competences in future journalists, it is necessary to conduct activities with activity games using interactive educational methods and factors influencing the student's personality.

Studying the abilities and opportunities of the student, comparing them with the personnel needs of the large structure in the regional mass media in the system. Practical activity in the production of information products organically included in the educational process in certain pedagogical conditions helps not only to strengthen the theoretical material, but also to personally verify their truth and effectiveness. Having a comprehensive and detailed form, the specially organized practical part of the educational process leads to the strengthening of the norms and values of professional culture and universal morality in the activity of the subject. The optimal complex form of mutual cooperation between the university and the broadcasting company is the establishment of a specialized experimental laboratory for the formation of professional qualifications of student journalists.

Professional qualification of journalists is a synthesis of three components: axiological, epistemological, praxeological.

The epistemological component includes certain general and special knowledge of journalism students needed to solve typical and non-standard professional tasks.

In this study, knowledge as a component of professional competence therefore represents three real levels: 1) low - reproductive, 2) medium - productive and 3) high - creative.

According to history, the importance of information has been known since ancient times. That is why different methods were used to protect information in ancient times. One of them is a mysterious inscription. The message in it could not be read by anyone other than the owner of the address to which the message was sent. For centuries, this art - mysterious writing - did not go beyond the upper classes of society, the residences of state embassies and intelligence missions. Only a few decades ago, everything changed radically, that is, information acquired its value and became a widely distributed commodity. It is now produced, stored, transferred, sold and bought. In addition, they steal, distort and falsify it. Thus, there is a need to protect information. The emergence of the information processing industry leads to the emergence of the information protection industry. As noted by I.L.Zelenkova, "if people suffering from "traditional deficiency" who understand freedom as arbitrariness on the basis of irresponsibility, act in the information society, the balance of this environment will be disturbed, its reputation will be lost. As a result, there will be a stable doubt about the voluntary information, which covers many people and will destroy the valuable direction in the future.

The policy of the state in the field of information is closely connected with the state policy of ensuring national security in the country. In this case, the information security system unites the main organizers of state policy into a single whole. This determines the role of information security and its position in the country's national security system. For example, in relation to states, "Sources of threats to information security are random and predictable".

Therefore, it would be appropriate to increase the media literacy competence of future journalists.

The integrity of the goals that reflect the national interests of Uzbekistan in the field of information, the strategic directions of their achievement and the systems of their implementation means the state information policy. One of the urgent issues is to create conditions that allow the implementation of state policy in the field of information security, to support the country's

economic and scientific-technical development, and to create methods and means of information protection. Practice shows that in order to achieve a sufficient level of progress in information protection, it is necessary to implement legal, organizational and technical measures together. It is determined by the confidentiality of the protected information, the classification of the threat and the availability of protective measures. In general, complex security measures include: - comprehensive protection against unauthorized use; - hardware and software tools; - complex means of cryptographic protection; – engineering and technical activities; - complex means of blocking technical channels; - physical security of objects can be included. Each of these measures complements the other, and the absence or deficiency of any method may result in a violation of the adequate level of protection.

The processes of global information globalization require not only the introduction of information and communication technologies into the economy and other sectors of countries, but also the provision of security of information systems. Uzbekistan was one of the first in Central Asia to join the international security system in the field of information and communication technologies.

It is necessary to increase the competence of future journalists to ensure information security, to identify sources of potential threats to the industry and to apply protective measures, and to develop the ability to analyze media texts. Because “sources of threats to information security are divided into internal and external sources”. Information is one of the main means of struggle for ownership of the modern world in the information age. So, in the era of globalization, information technologies and information management are developing at a high level. Therefore, future journalists should have full knowledge of working with the material and information promoted in the mass media.

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